

second means "unsteady in speech, unable to overcome small speech, not having the same work with speech". Therefore, the word "proverb" in Uzbek language has two meanings, firstly, it means "speech, speech" in the literal sense, and secondly, it means a widespread genre in folklore.

It influenced the emergence of proverbs, parables, and narrative genres, and due to the fact that the conclusion of parables and parables became a part of the story, it was sometimes confused with the terms of parables and parables. In fact, the word "parable" is also Arabic and means "similar", but in Uzbek it has two meanings, like a proverb and a metaphorical story aimed at explaining a purpose. However, by the 20th century, its use in the proverbial sense was limited. Only in Tajik folklore it was decided to call a proverb with the term "parable".

Although the word "Naql" remains in the proverbial sense, it is an Arabic word that means "to copy". In the Uzbek language, it has a secondary meaning like "narrate, tell a story, narrate" and remains as a scientific term representing an independent aphoristic genre of folk oral prose. In the proverb "A good saying is the root of the mind" is the meaning of "saying".

Proverbs are a widespread independent genre of oral artistic creativity as rare examples of folk wisdom. Conditionally, they can be called the rules of public etiquette. After all, proverbs are a phenomenon born from the very concise, concise, concise and figurative expression of the social-political, spiritual-cultural, moral-philosophical views of the people tested in their life experiences over the centuries. Proverbs are not specially created, but arise as a judgment as a moral assessment of the conclusion born from life experience tested due to the requirements of a certain situation. Although each nation's proverbs express the heart and national views of that nation, the meaning in them belongs to the whole nation. Due to these features, proverbs have acquired national and universal essence.

Proverbs were created in the form of a stable and unchanging, correct and truthful summary of the long-term life experiences of people in the course of their activities in various fields. Proverbs are in both poetic and prose forms, neither lyrical nor epic. For this reason, they, like riddles, idioms and figurative expressions, are included in the paremic type, and their recording and collection and reading pertains to paremiography, while their appearance, principles and laws of development, and art are organized in paremiology.

In proverbs, sayings are active, creating a unique inner rhyme and ensuring their harmony. There are different ways of classifying proverbs. In particular, grouping or classification according to alphabetical order, topics, synonymous or antonymic essence, literal or figurative meaning, and according to the social period in which it was created - chronology has become a tradition in paremiology. But so far, in Uzbek proverbs, the pineapple of alphabetical order and classification according to the topic has been followed in the compilation of the two-volume Uzbek folk proverbs (1987) and the multi-volume collection of Uzbek folk proverbs (1989) under the column "Uzbek folk art". Nevertheless, it can be observed that the history of recording Uzbek folk proverbs is very old and continued in two directions:

The first step is to record and read proverbs from the people as they are said in the live setting. The first recording and reading of Uzbek folk proverbs is associated with the name of Mahmud Kashgari, a great philologist of the 11th century. He was among many Turkic tribes and peoples, among other examples of folk art, he recorded many proverbs and published them in the work "Devonu Lugotit Turk", and on this basis he also started the practice of reading proverbs.

The practice of writing down Uzbek folk proverbs was continued by the poets Muhammadsharif Gulkhani and Sulaymongul Raji who lived and created in the end of the 18th century and the first half of the 19th century. Gulkhani found more than 400 folk proverbs, and Rojii 450, and collected them in their "Zarbulmasal". Of course, they did not collect proverbs for scientific purposes. In this, they mainly intended to strengthen folk appeal in their works, to individualize the language of the characters, and to achieve natural, simple expressiveness. Nevertheless, this service of theirs is particularly important in showing the historical progress of Uzbek paremiography.

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TABIATSHUNOSLIK FANIDA SINFDAN TASHQARI ISHLARNI ZAMONAVIY TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYA ASOSIDA TASHKIL ETISHNING AHAMIYATI.

Buxdipi 2-kurs magistranti

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Annotatsiya: ushbu tesizda tabiatshunoslik darslarida ekskursiya tashkil etishning zamonaviy metod haqida va ulardan foydalanishning usullari, ahamiyati haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ekskursiya, metod, zamonaviy ta'lim, pedagogik texnologiya, STEAM, inkorporatsiya.

Tabiatshunoslik darslarida sinfdan tashqari ishlarni zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari asosida tashkil etish sifatli ta'lim berishning eng samarali usuli hisoblanadi. Hozirgi kunda zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalarida STEAM, darsni inkorporatsion tashkil etish, ekskursiyalarni zamonaviy metodlar asosida o'tkazish kabilar kiradi. Xo'sh, STEAM texnologiyasi, inkorporatsion dars shaklining mazmuni nimada va ular qanday tashkil etiladi degan savolga javob topsak.

STEAM- real hayot talablaridan kelib chiqqan holda akademik ilmiy- texnikaviy konsepsiya doirasida integratsiyalashgan holda o'qitishdir. "STEAM texnologiyasi" fanda o'quv jarayonini tashkil etish va uning sifatini ta'minlash borasidagi zamonaviy yondashuvlar, innovatsion texnologiyalar sohasidagi ilg'or tajribalar modulli-kredit tizimi asosida ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, bo'lajak mutaxassislarni ixtisoslik fanlaridan ta'lim berish metodikasi, shakllari, metodlari, vositalari hamda o'qitishning ilg'or pedagogik va axborot texnologiyalariga oid bilim va ko'nikmalari shakllantiriladi. Masalan, 3-sinf Tabiiy fanlarga murojaat qiladigan bo'lsak, STEAM texnologiyasidan foydalanishning tayyor namunasi berilgan, loyiha va amaliy ish berilgan mavzu STEAM texnologiyasida integratsiya qilib berilgan. "Quyosh sistemasi modelini yasash" amaliy ish mavzusida (100-b) STEAM dan "S"-tabiiy fan quyosh haqida nazariy bilimlar beriladi, "T"-texnologiya quyoshning yasash jarayoni haqida tushuntiradi. Demak, ikki sohani Tabiiy fanlar quyosh sistemasi modelini yasashda Texnologiya fani bilan integratsiya qilinadi. Bu orqali o'quvchilar quyosh sistemasi haqida ham nazariy ma'lumotga ega bo'lishadi, ham ularning joylashuv o'rni va tarkibi haqida amaliy bajarib o'rganib olishadi, ham jamoaviy ish faoliyati tashkil etilib ular bilan kelishib ishlash ko'nikmasi ortib boradi. Jarayon davomida o'quvchilarni kasbga yo'naltirish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Bu mavzu orqali astronom, uchuvchi, kosmonavt, muhandislik, quruvchilik kasblari haqida ma'lumot berish va yo'naltirish mumkin.

Inkorporatsion dars shakli- Inkorporatsiya – kichikroq obyektlarni kattaroq obyektlarga kiritish. Korporatsiya (qonun) reglamentlarni tizimlashtirish turi.

Inkorporatsiya – lotincha "incorpore"- qonun ijodkorlik xususiyatiga ega bo'lmagan va ularni ma'lum asosda, me'zonda yagona to'plamlarga birlashtirishdan iborat bolgan normative-huquqiy hujjatlarni tizimlashtirish turi. (Umumiy huquq nazariyasining elementar tamoyillari)

Inkorporatsiya – ikki yoki undan ortiq asoslarning leksik ma'nosida avtonom bo'lgan bitta sintaktik morfologik yaxlitlikka birlashishi. Bu asoslar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarga mos keladi. (Katta ensiklopedik lug'at)

Inkorporatsiya – 1) o'z tarkibiga kiritish, boshqa tashkilotlarning qo'shilishi; 2) qonun hujjatlariga muvofiq bir guruh shaxslarga yuridik shaxs, korporatsiya maqomini berish; 3) davlat qonunlarini tizimlashtirish, ularning joylashuvi. (Iqtisodiy lug'at)

Demak, yuqorida berilgan "inkorporatsiya" atamasidan kelib chiqqan holda, ta'lim sohasida bu so'zni "fanlarni, bob va bo'limlarni, mavzularni bir-biriga bog'lash va o'quvchilarni mavzudan kelib chiqib kasb-hunarga yo'naltirish" deb qarasa, xato bo'lmaydi. inkorporatsiya so'zi integratsiyaga nisbatan keng tushuncha bo'lib, ichiga juda ko'p obyektlar va predmetlarni qamrab oladi. Integratsiya – o'quv faoliyatida o'zaro fanlarni bog'lash tushunilsa, inkorporatsiya- nafaqat